

Ce 21/Xianghu 14), Xiushui 24 (XS24 derived from (Ce 21/Xianghu 14)²/Xianghu 25), and Xiushui 11 (XS11, derived from CE 21²/Xianghu 25) were used to study the inheritance of resistance to three BI races, ZB₁₃, ZC₁₅, and ZE₁, during 1991-93.

The seeds of parents, F₁, and F₂ were sown in 60- × 30- × 7-cm plastic trays, one cross/tray. Seedlings were inoculated at the 4-leaf stage by spraying an aqueous spore suspension of 5 × 10⁴

conidia/ml. Disease reactions were scored about 10 d after inoculation.

The results indicated that two dominant genes controlled resistance to three BI races in XU84, XU25, XS04, and XS24, and only one dominant gene controlled resistance in XS11 (Table 1). Testing allelism of resistant parents indicated that some resistance genes were allelic, depending on BI races used (Table 2). ■

Senawee, Sufaida 172, ADR52, and ARC5752 were highly resistant to mealybug. N22, Rening, Oha, Sathra 265, and Katuyhar Dhan were moderately resistant (see table). ■

Pest resistance—insects

Resistance to rice mealybug in whitebacked planthopper-resistant rice varieties

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Resistance to rice mealybug (*Brevennis rehi*) was evaluated in rice varieties possessing diverse genes for resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) (*Sogatella furcifera*) using the seedbox screening test. Five replications were made. Pregerminated rice seeds were

sown in rows in a 30- × 25- × 6-cm seedbox.

At 7 d after sowing, each seedling was infested with 5-6 first-instar nymphs (crawlers). When about 90% of the susceptible check, TN1, had died, plant damage was rated on a 0-9 scale as 0 = no damage, 1 = slight damage, 3 = first and second leaves of most plants partially browned, 5 = pronounced browning and stunting or about half of the plants wilted or dead, 7 = more than half of the plants wilted or dead and remaining plants severely stunted and covered with a mealy coating, and 9 = all plants dead.

Rice mealybug damage ratings on rice varieties resistant to WBPH.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Gene for resistance to WBPH	Origin	Damage rating ^b
Boegi Boera	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Indonesia	5.8 b
N22	<i>Wbph 1</i>	India	3.4 cd
Muskhan 41	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Pakistan	2.2 def
Siam Garden	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Peru	3.0 cde
Rening	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Indonesia	4.2 c
Senawee	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Sri Lanka	1.0 g
Oha	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Nepal	3.8 c
Sathra 265	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Pakistan	3.8 c
Sufaida 172	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Pakistan	1.0 g
ADR52	<i>Wbph 3</i>	India	1.0 fg
Podiwi A8	<i>Wbph 4</i>	Sri Lanka	1.4 fg
N'diang Marie	<i>Wbph 5</i>	Senegal	1.4 fg
WC1240	<i>Wbph 1 + 1</i> recessive	India	3.0 cde
Katuyhar Dhan	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 2</i>	Nepal	3.4 cd
ARC5752	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 2</i>	India	1.0 fg
Colombo	<i>Wbph 2 + 1</i> recessive	India	3.0 cde
Chala Anaser	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 3</i>	Nepal	1.8 efg
TN1 (susceptible check)			9.0 a

^aMean of five replications. ^bIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

Resistance to thrips in traditional rice varieties

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We evaluated 100 traditional rice varieties for resistance to *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) under field conditions at the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, Coimbatore, during Oct 1993.

Pregerminated seeds were direct seeded in three 1-m rows. The resistant check, Ptb 21, and the susceptible check, TN1, were sown between every 10 test varieties. Varieties were exposed to natural thrip infestation. Damage was scored 30 d after sowing (DAS) using the 1-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

S. biformis population and plant damage ratings on traditional rice varieties under field conditions. Coimbatore, India, October 1993.^a

Variety	Population	Damage rating ^b
Co 2	9.0	cde 1.0 c
Co 4	8.2	def 1.0 c
Co 25	8.8	cde 1.4 c
Co 26	8.0	def 1.4 c
Co 27	7.8	def 1.0 c
Co 28	7.4	def 1.0 c
Co 30	7.4	def 1.0 c
ADT10	8.0	def 1.4 c
ADT25	9.8	cd 1.0 c
Ptb12	11.8	c 1.4 c
Ptb21 (resistant check)	6.0	f 1.0 c
PLR1	6.8	def 1.0 c
Thodavalan	9.0	cde 1.0 c
Kandagasalai	6.0	f 1.0 c
Valanchannel	8.8	cde 1.4 c
Chethuvali	7.8	def 1.4 c
Karuvali	6.6	ef 1.0 c
Kodagan	8.6	cdef 1.0 c
Vali	22.8 b	3.0 b
TN1 (susceptible check)	74.8 a	9.0 a

^aMean of five replications. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT. ^bScored using 1-9 scale in SES.

Eighteen traditional varieties had a damage rating of 1 in preliminary screening. They were retested to confirm resistance.

Treatments (varieties) were arranged in a randomized complete block design replicated five times. The resistant and susceptible checks were sown randomly among test entries. Water level was slightly increased at 7 DAS and maintained at the proper level. When susceptible check TN1 showed a rating of 7 at 20 DAS, 20 seedlings/replication were removed at random. Thrips were counted in each seedling under a binocular microscope and expressed as a mean population of thrips/seedling.

All of the selected traditional varieties had a low thrip population at 20 DAS, and all, except Vali, had a damage rating of 1, indicating a high level of resistance to thrips (see table). ■

Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) biotype in Karimnagar District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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The local gall midge (GM) Asian population at Agricultural Research Station, Warangal, AP, has biotype1 pattern and a resistant reaction to all three groups of differential donors (Eswarakora, Siam 29, and Veleuthacheera/Banglei derivatives). Since 1988, however, widespread GM incidence has been reported in resistant varieties Surekha and Phalguna in the adjacent district of Karimnagar. An experiment to examine GM biotype under natural field infestation was conducted during 1992 and 1993 wet seasons (WS) at RARS.

Eleven differential donors, constituting three different resistance groups, were obtained from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. Entries were transplanted in single rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing during the second week of Aug

Table 1. Reaction of differentials to GM population at RARS, Jagtial, AP, India. 1992 and 1993 WS.

Group	Entry	Differential donor	Incidence at 50 d after transplanting			
			Silvershoots on a tiller basis (%)		Damaged plants on a hill basis (%)	
			1992	1993	1992	1993
I	1	W1263	0	0	0	0
	2	ARC6605	0	0	0	0
II	3	Phalguna	30	26	100	95
	4	ARC5984	20	18	100	100
	5	Surekha	12	20	100	100
III	6	CR-MR-1523	3	0	40	0
	7	Velluthacheera	0	0	0	0
	8	Aganni	0	0	0	0
	9	Ptb10	0	0	0	0
IV	10	T1477	0	0	0	0
	11	TN1 (susceptible check)	38	30	100	100

Table 2. Reaction of different rice varieties and cultures to GM population in multilocation trials. RARS, Jagtial, Karimnagar, AP, India, 1992 WS.

Variety/culture	Parentage	Source of resistance	Reaction
Kakatiya	IR8/W1263	Eswarakora	Resistant
Pothana	IR579/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
Kavya (WGL 48684)	WGL 27120/WGL 17672 /Mahsuri/Surekha	Eswarakora and Siam 29	Resistant
Divya (WGL 44645)	WGL 23022/Surekha	Eswarakora	Resistant
Erramallelu (WGL 20471)	BC5-W/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
Dhanyalaxmi (BPT1235)	BC5-W/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
WGL 18011-15	CR44/W12708	Eswarakora	Resistant
Surekha	IR8/Siam 29	Siam 29	Susceptible
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	Siam 29	Susceptible
WGL 3962	Phalguna/IR36	Siam 29	Susceptible
WGL 3943	Phalguna/IR50	Siam 29	Susceptible

1992 and third week of Aug 1993 to favor high GM infestation. TN1 was used as the susceptible check. GM incidence was recorded for each entry by counting damaged hills, total tillers, and silvershoots at 50 d after transplanting.

GM incidence was heavy during 1992 WS. The group II differentials, Phalguna, ARC5984, and Surekha, and TN1 showed 100% damaged plants on a hill basis and 30, 20, 12, and 38% silvershoots, respectively, on a tiller basis. The group I differentials, W1263 and ARC6605, and group III differentials, CR-MR-1523, Velluthacheera, Aganni, and Ptb10, were free from GM

attack, except for CR-MR-1523, which had 40% damaged plants and 3% silvershoots.

A similar trend was noticed during 1993 WS. In group II differentials, Phalguna had 95% damaged plants with 2.6% silvershoots and ARC5984 and Surekha had 100% damaged plants with 18 and 20% silvershoots, respectively, compared with 100% damaged plants and 30% silvershoots in TN1. The other group I and II differentials were completely free from GM attack (Table 1).

In addition, previously GM-resistant varieties Phalguna and Surekha, derivatives of Siam 29, started showing